

PRIORITY PRINCIPLES OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENT APPROACH

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to determine the priority principles for the development of students' professional culture based on a competency-based approach.*

The current state of Uzbekistan's society, namely, the changes taking place in the political and economic spheres of the country's life, require a new perspective on the problem of personnel training in professional educational institutions.

In the organization of scientific and pedagogical activity, a serious approach is required to determine the principles that are the priority in the relevant process. Therefore, the correct, rational selection of priority principles leads to the comprehensive coverage of a certain process, not to neglect any factor.

The general principles of professional education are also taken into account when determining the priority principles in the process of developing the professional culture of college students based on the competence approach.

Vocational education is organized according to the following general principles: meeting the requirements of modern production; unity of theory and practice; training in the production process; vocational-polytechnic direction; independence; taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students; team teaching; setting a single pedagogical requirement and respecting the individuality of the student.

Keywords: *professional education, principles, vocational education, pedagogical requirement, individuality.*

The formation of an innovative educational environment requires the introduction of new principles into the teaching process, taking into account the social, economic, and cultural changes taking place in society. Based on this demand, the general principles of professional education have been enriched in recent years with the following: humanism of education and democratic ideals (organization of education based on taking into account the student's capabilities, needs and interests of the student community); connecting education with production work (reciprocity between training and development work, ensuring connection); professional mobility (ensuring that the content of education is in accordance with changing social situations, as well as achieving rapid adaptation of graduates to professional activities in different situations); modular teaching (organization of education according to modules (logically completed units); awareness (ensuring that students have a conscious approach to the educational process and professional activity); based on activity (achieving acceleration of the pace of students' educational activities during the educational process) and motivation (having a need that motivates students to organize professional activities in a practical way); openness for all (achieving education of citizens of the republic on the basis of equal rights in professions and trades) and demonstrability (organization of vocational education on the basis of instructions - performance or visual demonstration);

thorough acquisition of professional competence (attainment of the qualities of professional competence - knowledge, skills, competence, experience); goal orientation (training of qualified junior specialists as a social order), systematic (organization based on unity of structural elements consisting of all factors of education - purpose, tasks, organizational forms, methods, tools, technologies, result, teacher's and student's activities)¹; the result of education (qualified minor execution of a social order consisting in the training of a specialist); development of personal independence; motivation of teaching to professional activity; effectiveness of education; the availability of a favorable vocational training environment; economic expediency².

The object of research in the organization of scientific and pedagogical activity, its characterizing modern approaches along with the general principles of professional education based on its characteristic features work is also done based on the principles.

As a result of theoretical analysis, colleges with experimental sites, as well as observation of students' activities, organization of interviews with teachers and students, it was made sure that the following principles take priority in the development of the professional culture of college students based on the competence approach (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Priority principles of development of students' professional culture based on the competence approach

1. Axiological approach. Therefore, it is necessary to have a positive attitude towards it, to feel responsible for the organization of the workplace and the work process, to take care of work tools, tools, and tools, to ensure their suitability for work, to take the necessary measures for the long-term service of the machine, to maintain a high level of sanitary conditions in the workplace. It is required to achieve it, to save labor products, to show respect for professional traditions. On the basis of the competence approach, it is necessary to show the importance of work values in the development of the professional culture of college students, to form a positive attitude towards them.

2. The principle of problem-based teaching. Problem-based teaching occupies one of the main places in modern education. Therefore, problem-based teaching encourages the learner to think, propose several solutions to the problem, accept the optimal solution through their analysis, and justify it. In short, problem-based learning encourages the student to think comprehensively about the problem at hand. A person with the ability to think can fully express his potential and internal resources. This principle fully corresponds to the trend towards effective use of "human capital".

3. The principle of interactivity. One of the leading factors of teaching in an innovative educational environment is interactivity. Translated from English, the concept of "interactive"

means "to act together". According to the theoretical essence, interactivity represents the learning of educational materials and the performance of educational tasks based on mutual cooperation, harmony, and joint action of students in pairs, small and large groups. On the basis of interactivity, the movement of students aimed at acquiring and using new knowledge on the basis of "dialogue" with computer technology is also manifested.

In learning the science of "Metalworking technology" in colleges, the interactivity of the student and the group of students is visible in most cases in the process of completing educational tasks and working on machine tools. Working with metals, observing each other's practical actions during their processing, helping to understand mistakes, eliminating existing mistakes and shortcomings together, and coming to a final conclusion about practical actions are considered a bright example of interactivity.

4. The principle of project education. Project education also occupies a special place in modern education. Involvement of students in the implementation of educational, practical and creative projects creates in them the skills of thinking about professional issues, finding evidence, systematizing and analyzing thoughts, finding solutions in several options, determining the optimal solution among them, justifying and presenting the solution. It contributes to the fulfillment of the socio-pedagogical order of preparing a specialist with intellectual potential, and prepares students for effective professional activity in emergency situations.

5. The principle of innovative approach. Structurally, the core of the concept of "innovative approach" is the term "innovation". According to the dictionary meaning, the concept of "innovation" means "introducing something new" when translated from English. Introducing innovation in the educational process means enriching, changing and improving the teaching content, organizational forms, methods, tools, teacher's and student's activities based on new ideas. In the teaching of "Metalworking technology" in colleges, the organization of the process of mastering educational materials, involving students in completing educational tasks with the help of interactive methods, project, vitagen and development technologies indicates that professional education is being built on the basis of an innovative approach.

6. Principle of practical approach. The professional activity of "hand made" consists of a set of practical actions. This requires giving priority to practical training in the teaching of "Metalworking technology". Organizational-methodically correct organization of practical training in accordance with today's requirements should serve to develop the skills and competencies of students to work on machine tools, to fully understand the essence of professional activity, and to form a positive attitude towards it.

7. The principle of the Vitagen approach. From a lexical point of view, the concept of "vitagen" means "relying on life experience". Naturally, the basis of the professional culture of college students lies in their limited professional experience acquired during the social and practical training acquired in the process of interacting with the subjective being (those around them). On the basis of existing experiences, as well as during the period of practical professional activity, students gain experience by performing actions according to the necessary qualification requirements, and even by analyzing mistakes and shortcomings. The experience acquired during the lifetime of the students, added little by little in the general period of life and education, and in the end having "significant weight", serves as a "foundation" for the achievements they will achieve as a competent specialist in the future.

8. The principle of reflexivity. Like all international concepts, "reflexivity" has a specific meaning in the Uzbek language. According to the dictionary meaning, "reflexivity" when translated from English means "analysis of activity, behavior with hindsight". Theoretically, with the help of this concept, an effort aimed at analyzing oneself and one's own activity is expressed. Reflexive ability of college students helps them to independently analyze their learning and professional activities, to study the dynamic nature of professional knowledge, skills and competences, to recognize mistakes and deficiencies, and to search for ways to correct or eliminate them. A reflexive approach to continuous, consistent analysis of one's own performance teaches college students to critically evaluate their own behavior. This is one of the professional qualities necessary for a modern specialist. For this reason, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the development of the professional culture of their students based on the competence approach in colleges, so that they have reflexive abilities.

In conclusion, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the development of the professional culture of college students based on the competence approach of the above principles as a result of theoretical analysis, colleges with experimental fields, as well as observation of students' activities, organizing interviews with teachers and students.

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